

Design and Fabrication of Automated Scarecrow

Siddhant S Patil¹, Pranav A Kumbhar², Kartik S Patil³, Shrikant B More⁴, Vikas D Bate⁵, Sarvesh R Kurde^{6}*

ABSTRACT

To protect the produce in the fields from predators and catcalls, a scarecrow is utilized. To protect his crop from animals and catcalls, a planter places a scarecrow in the midst of the field. We've noticed that when birds enter the field, the scarecrow remains motionless. In our design, we'll change the scarecrow so that when birds enter the field, it will smell them with the aid of a sound detector, move its hand up and down with the use of a flapping medium, and begin buzzing with the aid of a buzzer. The flopping medium's job is to change the motor's rotational stir into the flopping hands' repaying stir. The birds will be scared away from the field as the coil rotates and the connecting rods drive the hand up and down, ensuring the safety of the field's crop. It may be used in the garden as well. A bait or dummy, typically in the form of a mortal, is the basis of a spontaneous scarecrow. Natural scarecrows are typically dressed in worn-out garments and left in open fields to discourage teasing and feeding on recently sown seeds and developing crops. Growers use scarecrows all around the world because they are a magnificent symbol of granges and, by extension, of the nation that engages in widespread agriculture. The typical or garden-style scarecrow is a constructed figure clothed in discarded clothing that is set up in open fields to discourage birds like crows and sparrows from disrupting and preying on recently sown seeds and developing crops. Windmills and other machinery are often mistaken for scarecrows, although this perception gradually fades as wildlife become accustomed to the structures. The nation's austerity is mostly supported by the money from tilling. When producers are far away from their crops and risk exposing them to dangers like bird catcalls destroying the crops, it causes them great anxiety.

Keywords: Scarecrow, Farmguard, E-Scarecrow

1. INTRODUCTION

With an automated scarecrow, large birds and other agricultural pests may be quickly and successfully managed (farm guard). The smart scarecrow is a tool commonly used by farmers to protect their crops from birds and animals. It is made by using old cloths and sticks, and is designed to have a scary appearance to frighten the animals away. This device is also used in gardens and airports for similar purposes. Unlike traditional scarecrows, which are ineffective at night, automatic smart scarecrows are a more efficient option for protecting crops from birds and animals.

Often referred to simply as "smart scarecrows," these devices provide all-time security to crops, and are effective both day and night. This makes them a superior option to traditional scarecrows for farmers and gardeners looking to keep their crops safe. The applications of scarecrow technology are numerous, including lowering financial loss due to crop damage brought on by birds and ensuring dependable, humane, and secure agricultural bird dispersal.

Producing different motions and sounds makes more impact than a static body. A recent report suggests that birds, while playing a significant role in fertilization and pest control, may also be causing a rare decrease in crop yields by destroying them. This is an emerging concern in agriculture, as avian species can cause economic losses to the farming community by damaging crops during planting, seedling, and maturing stages.

The report comes from the Committee on Doubling Farmer's Income (DFI), and highlights the need for improved methods of protecting crops from the harmful effects of birds. It's interesting to think about the delicate balance between the benefits of having birds in agricultural settings and the potential harm they can cause to crops.

1.1. BACKGROUND:

The first scarecrows known to humankind were built alongside the Nile River to keep quail flocks away from wheat crops. Wooden frames and nets were erected in the fields by Egyptian farmers. As a result, it has always been a challenge to safeguard agricultural production regions from numerous animals that have a propensity to harm the aforementioned places. Scarecrows are still used by farmers nowadays all over the world. Old men sit on seats and toss stones at birds that are trying to consume or harm farmers' crops in places like India and the Arab world.

Farmers have also tried using young boys as field patrollers to chase away animals or birds that were damaging crops physically, to scare them away by pounding sonorous objects like tin and jerry cans, and to produce noise to drive away birds (Wilfred, 2006). Nevertheless, this system's expense is a drawback, particularly for farmers with a sizable field plot. It has been suggested, for instance, to employ fixed objects like scarecrows to frighten birds away from a field. The usefulness of these gadgets, however, diminished quickly since the birds or other animals grew accustomed to them and lost their dread of them (Sullivan, 2011). It has been suggested that making a lot of noise would drive birds away from a field. An air pistol that ignites flammable gas at regular intervals can create such loud noise (Kim, 2011). But, after using loud noises repeatedly, birds become accustomed to them and the impact of frightening them lessens.

In a survey conducted in 2006 in the primary areas producing cereals (rice) in Uganda, Wilfred Odongola interviewed 1375 individual farmers, and 97.3% of them admitted that they were having issues with pests and illnesses attacking their crops, mainly birds and rats. In the crop's milky stage, birds eat, chew, and squeeze the grains. The grains are covered with milky white substances as a result of the damage. Birds harvest mature grains in their entirety. Moreover, birds perch on panicles, which causes crop lodging.

1.2. PROBLEM STATEMENT:

The use of scarecrows to protect crops from birds has been a longstanding tradition among farmers. In the past, birds could consume so much grain or wheat that a farmer and their family might not have enough food to last the winter. Scarecrows were created as a way to deter birds from feeding on crops, and have been used for generations by farmers around the world. Despite the invention of more sophisticated methods of crop protection, scarecrows continue to be a popular and effective tool for keeping birds away from crops in agricultural settings.

Farmers who grow paddy are experiencing significant losses in terms of quantity, quality, and monetary gains due to physical damage caused by birds feeding on their fields. Current traditional techniques, such as the use of static scarecrows, are only effective for small fields, leaving big commercial rice producers with the challenge of finding more effective solutions. Frightening birds using personnel is costly and not always available when needed. The use of avicides, which are harmful chemicals used to control bird populations, is one

example of a lethal practice that is not ecologically friendly and poses risks to both humans and birds. It is important for farmers to explore alternative, more sustainable methods of protecting their crops from bird damage that do not harm the environment or human health. The area of central Maharashtra has the problem of Birds that feed on crops, resulting to a reduction in the harvesting of farmers. As this area has low rainfall, the farms are dry, which leverages the birds to eat the crops. Due to hungry birds, the crops get destroyed. These birds eat as much as a crop in case they are going far away. Hence, this makes issue to farmers to protect the crop from these birds. It is only possible to safeguard the small area/land, but there is always a problem for big landholder farmers. The traditional scarecrow is not efficient due to static motion.

1.3.MAIN OBJECTIVES:

1. To design and construct a modern automatic scarecrow, using gears mechanisms, and sounds. Utilizing mechanical power and sound to scare away the birds and small animals.
2. To use Solar Panels to utilize the Renewable Energy Sources and power the mechanism.
3. To use the Sensors to detect the presence of birds in Farm.

2.COMPONENTS USED IN PROJECT:

1. Solar Panel (2X) - 25 Wattage
2. Spur gear (3X) - 6mm Diameter and 2.5mm Diameter
3. DC motor - 12V 60 RPM
4. Arduino Nano - ATmega328 AVR
5. Relay Module 5V
6. PIR Sensor - Range Up to 7m
7. Printed Circuit Board
8. Battery (12V)
9. Speaker
10. Rotating Arms (2X)
11. C Clamp
12. Nuts and Bolts
13. Structure -
 - 13.1. Main Square Tube
 - 13.2. Base plate
 - 13.3. Wooden house

2.1.WORKING :

Working of the project is divided into two parts one is mechanism working and another is circuit working. In the mechanism working, the flapping mechanism of hands is used to move the Scarecrow arm in an upward and downward direction. When the motor starts to run, the pinion gear mounted on the shaft of the motor starts to rotate. The two large gears are in contact with the pinion gear. So these two gear starts to rotate with the pinion gear. On the two large gears, a crank is connected at each gear. This crank is connected to the flapping arm at the one end and at the middle of the flapping arm, it is freely connected about which it can move upward and downward. Once the gear starts to rotate, the crank oscillates upward and downward. And flapping arm connected to the crank also starts to move upward and downward. This will give the motion to the automatic scarecrow.

Fig No.1.1 Connection Circuit

A PIR sensor in the circuit monitors the movement of birds and other animals and provides a signal to the microcontroller (Arduino Nano), to which the motor driver and batteries are linked. Further Arduino passes the signals to the motor driver from where it provides signals to the motor and Buzzer .

The code for above mechanism is design in such a way, that once a bird is been sense my sensor, the signal is passed to arduino and code is executed, this will allow initially to produce the sound for (10-20 sec), following my these time, the DC motor will be activated for (2 min), as the motor will complete 120 RPM, in given minutes. Hence , these mechanism will continue to do so, as the sensor senses the presence of birds. In this way, the energy is saved without affecting the quality of work delivered by Automated scarecrow.

Fig. No.1.2 Workflow diagram

2.2.DESIGN:

Fig. No.1.3.Overall Structure

Fig. No.1.4. Welding Details

Fig. No. 1.5. BOM

Fig.No.1.6.Dimensions

2.3.CALCULATIONS:

Weight of Solar Panels : 2.5kg,
 hence $2.5 \times 2 = 5$ kg of total head weight
 Initial Gear assumed diameter : 120 mm ,
 hence Total Displacement to be offered by Both the arms = whole diameter of gear = 120 mm
 Final Gear Diameter (Received in store) = 60 mm,
 hence Total Displacement achieved = 60mm
 Total Power consumption by Electric DC motor = $0.746 \times P(\text{Hp}) \times \text{load Factor} \times \text{time}$
 Assuming total working hour :
 If the motor works for every 2 min after every 20 min period, it will rotate 6min in 1 hour, that means in a day it will rotate on average of 72 min
 Assume load factor =1
 Therefore ,
 Total power consumption = $0.746 \times 0.014 \times 1 \times 72/60 = 0.01253$ Whr

2.4.MECHANICAL CALCULATIONS:

Bending Moment Diagram :

To calculate bending at the joint where , the acrylic plate is attached to threaded rod, first of all we need inputs,

The Threaded rod is of 100 mm length , which as one welded to structure and other loaded with mechanism,

The weight of the mechanism is about 250 grams,

Consider this all parameters,

$$M_x = R_a(L_a) \\ = 250 \times 100 = 25000 \text{ gforce.mm or } 0.00025 \text{ kN.m}$$

3.RESULT :

The Automated Scarecrow model performed his working well, but not at the mark, it was expected. It is due to the spur gears' diameter. As it was expected to have an oscillating arm with a minimum of 25cm of displacement, but due to a decrement in the gear diameter, leads to lower oscillating displacement. Replacement of gears will solve the problem of displacement. Regarding the speaker, it was up to the mark. It went on, as input was detected. And went off according to it was programmed. The solar panel does work with 80% efficiency, but it requires to be cleaned weekly. Cleaning solar panels is important otherwise, the efficiency would gradually decrease. Adding another source of power will also increase the time of the oscillating mechanism. It can be wind energy, but as of now, it will require another design to mount the turbine.

It is required to have a strong housing and protection to the electronic parts like Arduino. As it is seen in very bad condition like heavy rainfall may get damaged, hence protection of these parts are essential.

3.1.CONSLUSION:

Traditional Scarecrows are not able to provide overall satisfaction, it requires to use of technology to encounter the problem. Totally finishing the problem, is not the perfect solution for this problem. Birds are an important part of the environment, if it completely wiped out, will create an ecological imbalance. Now, that will create another problem. Hence, to have a good ecological balance, some amount of crops should not be preserved. It may be between 5-7%. The whole and soul of the project is to prevent a limited amount of crops from the birds.

Using technologies that may harm the birds, is against our mission. Hence, we had

taken care of such things best of our side. Using a limited sound, we kept the birds away and prevented the grains. The use of renewable energy like Solar was the best choice among all other renewable energies. As it provides energy in every corner of the world, it is not limited to mountains, plateaus, or plain grassland areas. It does not require costly maintenance, as it can be used in all seasons, including rainy ones. There are very few chances of birds to be arising in rainy seasons, as the crops are at their early stage, hence no more energy is required in such time.

The use of electronic technologies like Arduino and all different sensors are capable to work under severe conditions. It requires them to have strong housing, in some cases, it may not work due to the breakage of housing.

REFERENCE:

[1] Manoj Ashokrao Kale, studied the crop depredation done by birds in Deccan plateau in India, 2014. under which he explains the regions of highest depredation like Akola , Amravati districts from Maharashtra. The Study included interviews with farmers, identification of bird species responsible for act.

[2] Manoj Kale, studied the damage done by farm birds in agriculture. "Damage to agriculture yield due to farmland birds, present repelling technique and its impacts :an insight from Indian perspective" Article in Journal of Agriculture technology, 2012. This research analyzes the loss in yield of crops due to birds, explores repelling techniques adopted by the farmers, and addresses the consequences of integrated method of the bird diversity in India.

[3] Julie L. Elser, Catherine A. Lindell, Karen M. M. Steensma, Paul D. Curtis, Deanna K. Leigh "Measuring Bird Damage to Three Fruit Crops: A Comparison of Grower and Field Estimates ", 2019. "about major three crops, also they compared damage estimates obtained through field studies with estimates from a producer survey for three fruit crops: wine grapes, sweet cherries, and 'Honeycrisp' apples.

[4] Liba Pejchar, Yann Clough, Johan Ekroos, Kimberly A. Nicholas, Ola Olsson, Dafne Ram, Matthias Tschumi, And Henrik G. Smith " Net Effects of Birds in Agroecosystems ", 2018. discuss the merits and challenges of this concept, termed net effects, for birds in agroecosystems. They discuss the merits and challenges of this concept, termed net effects, for birds in agroecosystem.

[5] Sonia B. Cannvelli , Lyn C.Branch , Pedro Cavallero, Cristina Gonzalez, Maria Zaccagnini "Multi-level analysis of bird abundance and damage to crop fields" , 2014. explored habitat features influencing abundance and damage of monk parakeets (*Myiopsitta monachus*) to corn (*Zea mays*) and sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) fields, as a basis for the design and evaluation of management strategies for preventing damage in the future.

[6] Rahul Mapari, Kishor Bangale, Laukik Deshmukh, Prashant Gode, Ankit Gaikwad "Agriculture Protection From Animals Using Smart Scarecrow System", 2016. interaction between farmers and animals grows, resulting in conflicts. We investigated how raiding patterns fluctuate with different seasons, farm land, and crop varieties. And interaction between farmers and animals grows, resulting in conflicts. We investigated how raiding patterns fluctuate with different seasons, farm land, and

[7] MR Richardson , " Efficacy of Electronic Scare Crow On Four Mammalian Crop Raiders In Limpopo Province South Africa" , 2014. installed novel electronic scarecrows on two commercial citrus orchards and a private reserve and used video-recording remote cameras to assess crop raiders' reactions to them in Limpopo Province, South Africa.

[8] Shashank HN, Subhash H , Suhas R & Savita MM " Crop Protection And Animal Detection system" , IRJET< Volume 7 Issue 7, e-ISSN 2395-0056,2020. developed the system which will monitor the field using electronic technology.

[9] Stefano Giordano and Mike Ojo, David Adani & Fabio " IOT Solution For Crop Protection Against Wild Animal Attack" , DOI; 10.1109,EEL.2018.8385275, 2018. developed repelling and

a monitoring system is provided to prevent potential damages in Agriculture, both from wild animal attacks and weather condition.

[10] Aniket Siriya, “ A review of smart Agri ScareCrow’’, 2022. studied and prepared a smart scarecrow similar to look like humans. Using cranks, and connecting rods.